

The Fax and Teletext. Imagining the Future in the 1980s and 1990s

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The fax and Teletext were essential features of what in the 1980s and 1990s was referred to as the Information Age. Though technically different, they share important similarities. Engineers and managers in telecommunications often worked on both Teletext and the fax (Coopersmith, 2015, p. 5). Both took off in the early 1980s and quickly became era-defining. Both have been described as precursors to the Internet. Perhaps most importantly, both at the same time helped introduce and popularize the idea that information was and should be available almost instantly. In short, these “formidable” technologies (Moe & Bulck, 2016, p. 9) “changed the world” (Coopersmith, 2015, p. 1).

Despite their sociocultural importance, they have largely been neglected in media-historical scholarship (Coopersmith, 2015; Moe & Bulck, 2016). Moreover, existing literature focuses on *either* of these technologies in isolation, even though they were entangled (Verhoef, 2023a, p. 17).

This paper aims to fill this gap. It will answer the question: How were the fax and Teletext discussed *in relation to each other* in Dutch public discourse (1980-2000)? The Netherlands, known as “the ‘cockpit of Europe’ regarding media innovations” (Olderaan & Jankowski, 1989), provides a relevant case study as both technologies gained rapid and widespread popularity during the decades at hand.

Discourses about new media provide insights into the “multiple anxieties about the changing nature of everyday life” (Spigel, 1992, p. 3; Verhoef, 2022, 2023b, 2024) – in this case predominantly imaginaries about the (alleged) future. Dutch newspapers and magazines – i.e. existing media – frequently wrote about the fax and Teletext, for they deemed them defining features of the so-called Media Revolution and Information Revolution. By conducting a grounded-theory inspired discourse analysis of 30,000 digitized articles, this study will explore how these technologies were discussed *together* as part of a new media mix poised to change work, leisure, and communication (Verhoef, 2023a).

This research contributes to a better understanding of the interconnectedness of technologies during the often-neglected 1980s and 1990s, offering insights into the evolution of public perceptions and the impact of media innovations.

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